

EVALUATING THE EFFECTS OF TIRE POLLUTANTS 6PPD AND 6PPD-Q: AN
EXTENSIVE REVIEW COVERING SPECIES SPECIFIC AND INTRACELLULAR
TOXIC REPERCUSSIONS

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Abstract

2-((4-Methylpentan-2-yl)amino)-5-(phenylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione commonly known as 6PPD-Quinone, is the ozonized derivative of 6PPD. 6PPD is a common tire coating that acts as an antioxidant by preventing rubber degradation. Research efforts elucidating 6PPD-Q's toxicity surged after a 2021 study identified 6PPD-Q as an acute mortality inducing toxicant to coho salmon. This review functions as a comprehensive investigation of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's interaction with aquatic and terrestrial organisms. We also encompass studies providing toxicological explanations of dysregulation of intracellular activity such as transcription and metabolite transformation. This review aims to concurrently impart an overview of the most current 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies at organismal and cellular levels, emphasize research gaps, and propose possible routes for future studies.

Introduction

As transportation methods evolve so does the way we combat wear and tear on tires. In the rubber industry the lifetime of a tire is a big concern. Chemicals such as *p*-phenylenediamine (PPD) are a class of antioxidant and antiozonant molecules used to coat tires to prevent breakdown and prolong their usage.¹ Originally discovered in the 1960s, 6PPD, *N*-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-*N'*-phenyl-*p*-phenylenediamine, quickly became the gold standard antiozonant. As of today, there is no alternative antiozonant tire coating available.

6PPD has become a prominent environmental pollutant in recent years. When entering the environment 6PPD can react with ozone creating *N*-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-*N'*-phenyl-*p*-phenylenediamine-quinone (6PPD-Q).² These two molecules, as ubiquitous as they are, readily enter the environment through road run-off and accumulate in both rural and urban waterways (Table 1). The half-life of 6PPD is approximately 5 hours in water compared to 6PPD-Q which has a half-life of about 33 hours.³ Long term persistence of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q has raised concern for aquatic life subjected to these chemicals.

As more information surrounding 6PPD is published, a trend of mortality in coho salmon has become apparent. Coho salmon dwell in freshwater streams, typically near highly urbanized areas.⁴ As these urban areas expand, more road runoff is produced leading to detrimental effects in nearby streams. Increased mortality rates of coho salmon required deeper investigation that led to the discovery of PPDs as an environmental toxin. The accumulation of PPDs seem to impact coho salmon at higher rates than other freshwater species.

The coho salmon mortality discovery has opened the door to a new field in environmental toxin research. Slowly, more publications have revealed species, zebrafish specifically, with higher tolerances to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q^{3,5-15}, effects on humans living in areas with high rubber recycling¹⁶⁻²⁰, as well as metabolites and transcriptional changes in species and cell lines when exposed to PPDs.^{3,9,21-25}

Although other 6PPD reviews have been published covering environmental impacts, this review aims to summarize what is known thus far about the toxic effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in aquatic organisms, model organisms, and human cell lines.²⁶⁻³⁰ Conversions of environmental concentrations ($\mu\text{g/L}$) of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q to molar concentrations are displayed for easy comparison between *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies (Table 2). What is known about 6PPD, and 6PPD-Q is scarce with only a few

discoveries agreeing between studies. To drive scientific discovery, major gaps regarding EPA regulation, detection of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in the environment, non-aquatic model organisms, and limited omic research in cell lines need to be addressed. To remedy these missing pieces of the puzzle, the underlying toxic mechanism of PPDs needs to be uncovered to better understand ways to combat its toxicity.

Table 1. Countries with 6PPD or 6PPD-Q detected in local samples.

Country	Location of Sample Site	Chemical	References
Argentina	Buenos Aires	6PPD-Q	[³¹]
Australia	Queensland (Brisbane River)	6PPD-Q	[^{32,33}]
Brazil	São Paulo	6PPD-Q	[³¹]
Canada	Southern Ontario (Don River & Highland Creek) & Toronto	6PPD-Q	[^{31,34–36}]
Chile	Santiago	6PPD-Q	[³¹]
China	Guangzhou (Liuxi River & Guanghua Basin), South China (Greater Bay Area), Guangdong (Pearl River & Dongjiang river), Zhejiang (Zhujiang river & Jiaojiang River), Yangtze River, Taiyuan, Zhengzhou, Shanghai, Nanjing, Hangzhou, & Hong Kong	6PPD & 6PPD-Q	[^{23,37–48}]
Columbia	Bogota	6PPD-Q	[³¹]
Germany	Leipzig Saxony	6PPD & 6PPD-Q	[^{49–52}]
India	Kolkata & New Delhi	6PPD-Q	[³¹]
Japan	Tokyo	6PPD-Q	[^{31,53}]
Nigeria	Lagos	6PPD-Q	[³¹]
Poland	Warsaw	6PPD-Q	[³¹]
Spain	Madrid	6PPD-Q	[³¹]
USA	California (San Francisco Bay), Colorado, Georgia, Kansas, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi (Oxford), New York, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Oregon, Texas, Virginia, & Washington (Tacoma)	6PPD-Q	[^{31,54–57}]

Table 2. Common concentrations of 6PPD* and 6PPD-Q* listed as micrograms per liter (µg/L) and corresponding conversion to nanomolar (nM).

6PPD (µg/L)	6PPD (nM)	6PPD-Q (µg/L)	6PPD-Q (nM)
0.1	0.370	0.1	0.340
5	1.86	5	1.68
10	3.73	10	3.35
50	18.6	50	16.8
100	37.3	100	33.5
500	186	500	167.6
1000	373	1000	335

*Based on molar masses 6PPD, 268.4 g/mol and 6PPD-Q, 298.4 g/mol

Aquatic Organisms

1. Coho Salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*)

Many efforts have been made to thoroughly investigate the consequences of tire surfactant particles on coho salmon. Coho salmon are of high ecological importance because of well-documented “coho pre-spawn mortality” of adult coho salmon returning to spawn. A 2021 study was the first to evaluate mortality in coho salmon following “recognition” of the ecological phenomena (Table 3). Researchers used juvenile coho salmon as a stand-in representative of adult coho salmon. 6PPD-Q was found to be highly toxic with the mean lethal concentration being $0.79 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g/L}$ 6PPD-Q.^{58,59} In an adult coho salmon study, acute mortality was found to be induced at a slightly higher concentration of 1.3 to 1.8 µg/L 6PPD-Q. Both behavioral and physiological changes were also induced. Exposed salmon exhibited changes in behavior ranging from lethargy to complete immobilization. Physiological blood parameters indicated a significant increase in hematocrit suggesting cardiorespiratory distress.⁶⁰ Most recently, coho salmon embryos have been tested for growth and survival effects following 6PPD-Q exposure. Multiple 6PPD-Q exposures found significant embryonic mortality was observed at 7.22 µg/L as 79% of treated embryos failed to hatch. Additionally, 21% of the treated embryos, significant adverse development and growth was observed.² Though scientists have reached coordinating conclusions regarding the mortality effects of 6PPD-Q in coho salmon, knowledge gaps concerning behavioral, morphological, and physiological effects throughout the life cycle remain. Research efforts have instead trended towards expanding upon 6PPD-Q effects on other aquatic organisms.

2. Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)

a. Morphological changes

Zebrafish embryos and larvae are a popular model organism being used to investigate the effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q because they are considered a “tolerant” species.¹³ Their short gestational times and transparent bodies make morphological

studies simple. Several studies have used zebrafish to examine effects of environmental levels of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. In three studies, treatment of 6PPD and its quinone derivative induce various morphological transformations and mortality rates in zebrafish (Table 3). In 2022, Vashney et. al., discovered the lethal concentration at 96 hours for 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in zebrafish to be 442.62 µg/L and 132.92 µg/L respectively.⁵ This has been contradicted more recently in 2024 when Chang et. al published a 120-hour LC₅₀ of 0.87 mg/L (870 µg/L) for 6PPD.¹⁵ This is a stark increase in concentration at a longer exposure time compared to what was previously published. The effect of 6PPD across various studies at different concentrations have varied but still yielded morphological changes. 6PPD causes a decrease in eye development and size, hatchability, body length, and reduced swim bladder size.^{5,7,10,11,15} Between the studies there is controversy over the effects of 6PPD on hatchability and body length. Additionally, in zebrafish exposed to 6PPD-Q, there are no significant changes to eye or bladder development but increased instances of lordosis, kyphosis and malformations of the tail.^{5,11,13,15} Additional studies covering the lethal concentration and morphological effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q should be conducted to fully understand the extent of effects.

b) Behavioral changes

Zebrafish have also been used to study behavioral changes when exposed to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. When exposed to the chemicals separately, zebrafish exhibited a decrease in swimming distance and velocity.^{5,7,13} The virtual motor response (VMR) and vibrational startle response (VSR) were not affected in the presence of 6PPD-Q but significant changes were observed in the sleep wake cycle when subjected to light-dark cycles.¹³ Zebrafish, when exposed to 2000 ng/L of 6PPD-Q, had increased frequency of sleeping bouts and slept more frequently throughout the light periods.¹³ Moreover, the phototactic behavioral response of zebrafish, behavior in response to light, was significantly decreased when exposed to 6PPD but not 6PPD-Q.¹⁵ Additional studies are needed to address the differences between the effects of the two chemicals.

c) Physiological changes

Aside from morphological and behavioral changes induced by PPDs, zebrafish also have shown various physiological changes, some even linking to the changes in behavior. 6PPD and 6PPD-Q affect heart rate, cardiac output, oxygen consumption, hormone levels and regulation of neurotransmitters. Although these effects span different biological functions, many of these studies have contradicting conclusions. Vashney et. al., studied the effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q on heart rate and cardiac output, finding that both chemicals at 25 µg/L decrease heart rate, cardiac output and oxygen consumption.⁵ A different study concluded that upon exposure to 6PPD-Q there is a significant increase in heart rate but no difference in oxygen consumption.¹³ Within the same study there is further controversy about the up and down regulation of neurotransmitters. Ricarte et. al, found that 6PPD-Q increases the levels of norepinephrine while no changes can be seen in dopamine. This was contradicted in a different study that found 6PPD-Q decreases dopamine and does not affect norepinephrine levels.⁷ The controversy continues regarding thyroid function. 6PPD has been found to significantly increase the levels of T4 without altering the levels of T3.¹⁵ These findings differ from Peng et. al, who found that 6PPD causes a decrease in levels of T3.¹¹ T3 and T4 are influential hormones in eye development in zebrafish which are

affected by 6PPD. These differential findings emphasize the need for further studies confirming or negating the effects of PPDs on physiological changes in zebrafish.

Terrestrial Organisms

1. Mice (*Mus musculus*)

Toxic effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q have also recently started to be studied in mammalian models such as male mice and rats. Male mice offer a good fertility model because of their short reproductive times. 6PPD-Q has been found to be reproductively toxic to male mice (Table 3).⁶¹⁻⁶⁷ When subjected to 6PPD-Q, testosterone levels decreased as well as the quality of sperm declined which is needed for *in vitro* fertilization (IVF).⁶⁶ Additionally, pathways involving spermatogenesis and sphingolipid metabolism were differentially affected after exposure to 6PPD-Q for 40 days at 4 mg/kg.⁶⁶ At even lower doses, 10 and 100 µg/kg 6PPD-Q caused intestinal inflammation, in the ileum and jejunum, in mice, which was further confirmed by increased levels of TNF-α, IL-1, and IL-6, inflammatory cytokines.⁶³ Additional inflammatory cytokines, TNF-α, IL-10 and IL-6, were observed in the lungs of male BALB/c mice after repeated injection of 6PPD-Q in a bioaccumulation study.⁶² A third study exposed male C57BL/6 mice to 6PPD-Q over a prolonged period and saw similar inflammatory cytokines, increased levels of ROS, apoptosis and blood-brain barrier disruption.⁶⁴ 6PPD-Q has also been found to contribute to hepatotoxicity in male mice and rats. Long term exposure to 6PPD-Q leads to elevated lipid deposition and short-term exposure affected glucose and riboflavin, essential for liver health, and metabolism.⁶⁵ These selected mice and rat studies highlight the various toxic effects of 6PPD-Q. Additional studies focusing on female fertility need to be implemented to push the understanding of the toxic mechanisms of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.

2. Humans (*Homo sapiens*)

To better understand the effects of 6PPD and its quinone derivative on human health populations, epidemiology studies were carried out in areas with high electronic and rubber waste disposal. Specifically in these areas, in industrialized China, children from ages 2-7 underwent urine analysis to detect PPDs compared to a control group located farther from the waste disposal. The median levels of PPDs were higher for the group in closer proximity to the waste plant.¹⁶ Dust samples from areas with high levels of rubber recycling compared to a control also exhibited higher urine concentrations of 6PPD. This was further associated with a decrease in BMI, alteration of the gut microbiota and more frequent illnesses such as influenza compared to areas with low rubber recycling (Table 3).^{17,18} Ingestion of dust in toddlers, approximately 3.48 ng/kg bw/d, was also tracked to indoor venues through paint and flooring materials.¹⁹ Although the main focus this far has been on 6PPD's effect in children a few studies have also detected PPDs in breastmilk and adult urine.²⁰ This raises concerns that these tire pollutants may be passing from parent to child. More studies encompassing dust exposure, human excretions, and transgenerational transmission will give greater insight on exposure level so a tolerance level can be established.

3. *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*)

While 6PPD-Q is often confirmed to be in rivers, creeks, and seas, it has also been found in dirt and air samples. *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) offer unique insight upon 6PPD-Q exposure as while they are often terrestrial, they can also be

found in aquatic environments. The first study regarding *C. elegans* treated the nematodes with 6PPD-Q concentrations ranging from 0.1-100 µg/L. At the highest concentration of 100 µg/L 6PPD-Q, mortality was induced in 5% of nematodes (Table 3). The researchers noted it was nowhere near complete sample mortality but was still a significant increase when compared to the control.⁶⁸ Though mortality is uncommon in *C. elegans*, three studies found 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in a decreased lifespan.⁶⁹⁻⁷¹

Two studies found treatment of lower 6PPD-Q concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 10 µg/L resulted in decreased and abnormal locomotion.⁷² Decreased locomotion was hypothesized to be caused by the neurodegeneration observed in D-type neurons following exposure to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q.⁷³ Neurodegeneration was also observed in dopaminergic, glutamatergic, serotonergic, and GABAergic neurons causing decreased sensory perception and neurotransmission.^{72,74} Conjunctively, exposure to 1 to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q resulted in a decrease of dopamine synthesis leading to a decrease of dopamine related behavior.⁷⁵

No morphological changes were indicated in any *C. elegans* studies, however, increased intestinal permeability was found in nematodes treated with 1 to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q.^{68,76} Metabolism appears to be broadly affected as an increase in fatty acid synthesis resulted in lipid accumulation. Glycogen and glucose metabolism are inversely affected as 6PPD-Q results in an increase of glycogen metabolism and a decrease of glucose metabolism.⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰ Recent research has trended towards studying changes in metabolism within *C. elegans*, however, many more metabolic pathways stand to be studied.

Table 3. Summary of 6PPD & 6PPD-Q effect on aquatic animals, terrestrial animals, and humans

	Chemical treated	Effects	References
Coho Salmon	6PPD-Q	Mortality induced in embryonic, juvenile, & adult forms Morphological: decreased size Behavioral: lethargy and immobilization Physiological: increased hematocrit	[2,58-60]
Zebrafish	6PPD & 6PPD-Q	Mortality induced Morphological: decreased eye development and size, hatchability, body length, and swim bladder size Behavioral: decreased swimming abilities, increased sleeping, & decreased phototactic behavioral response Physiological: altered affect heart rate, cardiac output, oxygen consumption, hormone levels and regulation of neurotransmitters	[5,7,10,11,13,15,60]

Rotifer	6PPD	Mortality & decreased population growth	[81]
Brook Trout	6PPD-Q	Physiological: increased interlamellar cell mass (ILCM) size, hematocrit, blood glucose, & total CO ₂ Decreased blood sodium & chloride concentration	[82]
Rainbow Trout	6PPD-Q	Acute mortality Physiological: increased cardiorespiratory, respiration, & metabolism	[83,84]
Arctic Char	6PPD-Q	Physiological: increased metabolism	[83]
Late Trout	6PPD-Q	Mortality Morphological: Caudal fin & eye deformities	[85]
Mice	6PPD & 6PPD-Q	Physiological: Decreased testosterone, sperm quality, Altered spermatogenesis, and sphingolipid metabolism pathways Increased inflammation & lipid accumulation	[62-66]
Humans	6PPD & 6PPD-Q	Physiological: decreased BMI, altered gut microbiome, & increased susceptibility to illnesses	[16-20]
<i>C. Elegans</i>	6PPD-Q	Moderate lethality Behavioral: altered locomotion Physiological: increased intestinal permeability, neurodegeneration, lipid accumulation, & glycogen metabolism. Decreased glucose metabolism & dopamine synthesis	[68-80]

Cellular Level Interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q

1. Metabolomics

The metabolic fate of 6PPD-Q is still largely unknown. Various *in vivo* and *in vitro* models including, rats, trout, zebrafish, human urine and various liver cell lines, have been used to discern the Phase I and Phase II metabolites. Phase I metabolites are the first modification of the original compound and Phase II metabolites are the subsequent modifications of Phase I molecules. Across all models the main chemical transformations of 6PPD-Q fall into hydroxylation and oxidation for Phase I, and glucuronidation and sulfation for Phase II metabolites.^{3,9,21,22,24,25} In the rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) model, the RTL-W1 cell line was used to study liver metabolites

of 6PPD-Q. The researchers found the CYP1A, a type of P450 enzyme, is likely responsible for many of the biotransformation's of 6PPD-Q.²² One example of the Phase I metabolite in the trout model was hydroxylation of the alkyl side chain. A Phase II metabolite includes glucuronide conjugated transformation products. This study inferred the addition of glucuronide and sulfide is thought to increase hydrophilicity which in turn promotes easier elimination.^{21,25} These modifications could contribute to the higher tolerance of 6PPD-Q in rainbow trout.

Although there are common metabolites of 6PPD-Q, transformation speeds vary. In mice and zebrafish, the metabolism of 6PPD-Q is rapid and occurs within 24 hours of exposure.^{3,9,25} The rapid modification of 6PPD-Q could be the reason behind the higher tolerance in zebrafish and mammalian models. The hydroxylated Phase I metabolites showed no predicted toxic effects after using a modeling system.²⁵ This however needs to be studied more in depth because many Phase II metabolites with different modifications may still induce toxic effects.³ In one study, differences between two human liver cell lines, cancerous HepG2 and noncancerous L02 cells, were found to have differential effects when exposed to 6PPD-Q. Only Phase I metabolites were seen in the L02 cells while both Phase I and II were found in HepG2 cells.²⁴ This difference needs further clarification to see why L02 cells have lower metabolic rates of 6PPD-Q. Since many models studied thus far have similar Phase I modifications, hydroxylation could be used as a potential biomarker for 6PPD-Q exposure.

Only one study has investigated the metabolites of 6PPD in zebrafish. Only Phase II metabolites were detected, most likely because of the fast transformation rate of 6PPD. The most common metabolite detected was 4-HDPA, a hydroxylated derivative of 6PPD.³ Little information is known about the toxic effects of 4-HDPA. Comparing the results of 6PPD-Q metabolites to those seen in 6PPD metabolic pathways will help discern the toxic mechanisms of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.

2. Transcriptomics

Researchers have used transcriptomics to further understand the mechanisms by which 6PPD and 6PPD-Q induce toxic repercussions. Transcriptomics of organisms known to be in direct contact with 6PPD-Q, such as coho salmon, reveal dysregulation of various transcripts. Dysregulated transcripts encoding proteins that mediate the blood brain barrier and vascular permeability were affected in a dose dependent manner ranging from 0.1 to 7.2 µg/L.² 6PPD-Q is also thought to dysregulate the immune system as expression of proinflammatory genes *tnfa* and *il1β* were upregulated.²

In zebrafish, 6PPD and 6PPD-Q each cause differential expression of genes related to various signaling pathways, morphological, and physiological effects. Exposure of 2.2 mg/L 6PPD altered genes regulating the thyroid signaling pathway. 6PPD also altered expression of genes involved in development of the eye like *rpe65a* and *opn1lw1*.^{11,15} 6PPD induced lipid accumulation was also verified by an increase in genes regulating lipid synthesis and metabolism.^{86,87} Zebrafish exposed to 6PPD-Q, concentrations ranging from 0.25 to 25 µg/L, experienced dysregulation of genes regulating estrogen signaling in a dose dependent manner. 6PPD-Q also downregulated the expression of *per1a*, *per3*, and *cry3a* involved in circadian rhythm regulation.^{12,13}

In mice, both 6PPD and 6PPD-Q were found to alter hepatic metabolism by upregulated genes promoting immune responses.⁶¹ Another study found altered

expression of Ripk1, Fadd, Il-6st, and Il-16 further confirming a change in the immune system.⁶²

One study found *C. elegans*, when exposed to 0.1 to 10 µg/L 6-PPDQ, significantly increased their expression of antioxidant genes like *sod-2*, *sod-3*, & *sod-4*.⁶⁸ These findings were partially backed by another study that found an upregulation of the genes related to the mitochondrial unfolded proteins response (mt UPR) *atfs-1*, *ubl-5*, and *dve-1* at low concentrations of 6PPD-Q (0.1 and 1 µg/L).⁸⁸ At high concentration these same three genes were found to be downregulated. The mt UPR indicates stress within the mitochondria and can often lead to the upregulation of antioxidant enzymes.⁸⁹ Lipid accumulation is also found to be upregulated. This is explained by an increase in transcription of fatty acid synthesis genes *fasn-1* and *pod-2*, and a decrease in transcription of genes *acs-2* and *ech-2* related to fatty acid oxidation.⁷⁷

Most recently, an *in vitro* endometrial epithelial study demonstrated exposure to 1 µM 6PPD-Q downregulated endometrial receptivity genes, like IL6, whereas 1 to 10 µM 6PPD upregulated genes, for example, TNFα, encoding inflammatory.⁹⁰ Collective transcriptomic profiling indicates a slight trend in the upregulation of immune responses across coho salmon, mice, and some human epithelial cells (Table 4). However, most transcriptomic research indicates 6PPD and 6PPD-Q enact species dependent effects on gene transcription. In the future, research regarding transcriptomic analysis on various human cell lines may verify or nullify any overlap between species' transcriptomic mediated 6PPD and 6PPD-Q effects.

Table 4. Transcription dysregulation in Coho Salmon, Zebrafish, Mice, *C. elegans*, and epithelial cells and their morphological effects.

	Chemical treated	Transcripts dysregulated	Alterations to
Coho Salmon	0.1-7.2 µg/L 6PPD-Q	<i>tnfα</i> , <i>il1β</i> , <i>JAM</i> , & <i>ifny</i>	Blood brain barrier, vascular permeability, & inflammation
Zebrafish	0.25-25 µg/L 6PPD-Q & 2.2 mg/L 6PPD	<i>rpe65a</i> , <i>opn1lw1</i> , <i>per1a</i> , <i>per3</i> , & <i>cry3a</i>	Thyroid signaling pathway, eye development, estrogen signaling & circadian rhythm
Mice	10-100 mg/kg 6PPD & 6PPD-Q	Ripk1, Fadd, Il-6st, & Il-16	Immune system, macrophage infiltration, & prostate cancer activation
Endometrial epithelial cells	1-10 µM 6PPD & 1 µM 6PPD-Q	<i>tnfα</i> , IL6, & TGFβ1	Endometrial receptivity and inflammatory responses
<i>C. elegans</i>	10 µg/L 6PPD-Q	<i>atfs-1</i> , <i>ubl-5</i> , <i>dve-1</i> <i>fasn-1</i> & <i>pod-2</i>	Mitochondrial unfolded protein response & lipid accumulation

3. Protein interactions

To further verify experiments assessing a protein's binding affinity to 6PPD or 6PPD-Q, researchers are using newly discovered molecular docking software that efficiently predicts a protein's binding affinity to chemical compounds. A preliminary *in vitro* assay demonstrated cytochrome P450's ability to transform 6PPD into 6PPD-Q within human liver microsomes.⁹¹ An enzyme inhibition assay then identified CYP1A2 as the most critical cytochrome involved in the further transformation of 6PPD-Q. Molecular docking was then used to confirm 6PPD-Q strongly bound to CYP1A2.²¹

Recently, researchers have prioritized using molecular docking software to confirm 6PPD-Q's impact on *C. elegans*. Results indicate 6PPD-Q has a widespread protein binding ability within *C. elegans*. 6PPD-Q has been found to cause neurodegeneration after activating ion-channels MEC-4 and DEG-3.⁷³ Molecular docking then confirmed the presence of specific binding sites within MEC-4 and DEG-3. Neurotransmission was further shown to be altered as nematodes introduced to 6PPD-Q had reduced levels of dopamine, serotonin, glutamate, and dopamine. This was confirmed by molecular docking indicating 6PPD-Q binding sites on neurotransmitter synthesis proteins.⁷²

Despite 6PPD-Q being a related ozonized counterpart of 6PPD, research often shows stark contrast regarding the effects of both chemicals. 6PPD bound to human serum albumin (HSA) resulted in activation of the esterase activity whereas 6PPD-Q binding to HSA inhibited its esterase activity. Molecular docking was used to investigate this dichotomy. Software confirmed 6PPD and 6PPD-Q each interacted with amino acid residues on HSA. The higher binding affinity of HSA to 6PPD was a result of 6PPD's more negative surface potential.⁹²

Some studies are relying entirely on molecular docking software to evaluate 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's ability to bind to specific proteins.^{93,94} While molecular docking has been proven to be an increasingly valuable resource, the importance of continuing to include experimental data confirming the predicted binding properties of a protein *in vitro* cannot be understated.

4. Epigenetics

As of March 2025, only one study has linked epigenetic changes in *C. elegans* to exposure to 6PPD-Q. When exposed, *C. elegans* can employ the mitochondrial unfolded protein response (mt UPR) to ensure the mitochondria continues to function at a normal capacity.⁹⁵ Under stress conditions the mt UPR is employed in nematodes using genes *atfs-1*, *ubl-5* and *dve-1*. These genes are under control by upstream histone methyltransferases, *set-6* and *met-2*, and histone demethylases, *jmjd-1.2* and *jmjd-3.1*. Upon treatment of 6PPD-Q at 1 and 10 µg/L, *met-2* and *set-6* exhibited an increase in mRNA levels while *jmjd-1.2* and *jmjd-3.1* showed a decrease in mRNA levels.⁸⁸ The change in expression of these genes lead to a decrease in activation of the mt UPR response making the nematodes more susceptible to toxic effects of 6PPD-Q.⁸⁸ This study only scratched the surface of epigenetic changes within one species. Additional studies investigating 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in different model organisms, site specific DNA methylation, histone modification and transgenerational epigenetic effects will give better insight to the long-term effects of these environmental pollutants.

Conclusion

1. Reactive Oxygen Species

Wide scale research has been done regarding 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's aptitude to increase oxidative stress within the cell as indicated by an elevation in reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels. Common ROS formed often include superoxide anions, hydroxyl radicals, and hydrogen peroxide.⁹⁶ 6PPD increased ROS levels in embryonic, larval, and adult zebrafish.^{6,10,11,97-99} Following studies focusing on aquatic animals at high risk of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q exposure, researchers have also studied plants and algae at similarly high risk of exposure. 6PPD was found to increase oxidative stress in microalgae whereas 6PPD-Q increased ROS levels in various aquatic plants.¹⁰⁰⁻¹⁰² Aquatic plant studies also indicate 6PPD-Q exposure results in more oxidative stress than 6PPD. Many studies find 6PPD-Q also induce ROS within human cell lines like L02 and HepG2 as well as *C. elegans* and mice.^{24,64,68,76,103,104}

Following increased levels of ROS, antioxidant proteins may mitigate the harmful effects of oxidative stress. Studies have found an increased expression of antioxidant proteins like SOD-2, SOD-3, and SOD-4 following PPD exposure as seen in Figure 1.^{68,94} 6PPD and 6PPD-Q also directly increase the activity of antioxidant proteins.¹⁰⁵ RNAi further confirmed the importance of antioxidant species following PPD exposure. SOD-3 is a common downstream target of DAF-16.⁷⁰ RNAi of *daf-16* resulting in increased susceptibility to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's production of ROS because of decreased activation of antioxidant proteins.^{79,88,103} RNAi of SOD-2 and SOD-3 also increased *C. elegans*' susceptibility to ROS.⁷¹ Studies continue to focus on 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's effect on ROS levels as ROS indicates cellular damage and promotes inflammation pathways.

2. Inflammatory Response

Extensive research has been done regarding 6PPD and 6PPD-Q induced inflammation in mammals. One study found 6PPD-Q elevated common cytokines TNF- α , IL-1, and IL-6 levels in mice.⁶³ Cytokines are crucial signaling molecules in the inflammatory pathway.¹⁰⁶ 6PPD-Q was found to specifically induce neuroinflammation in mice as it increased cytokines TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β as well as microglia.⁶⁴ Inflammation within mice lungs following 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in increased cytokine levels as well as increased expression of genes regulating inflammation responses like Ripk1, Fadd, Il-6st, and Il-16.⁶² 6PPD and 6PPD-Q also cause inflammation within human lung cells as both PPDs induce an increase in proinflammatory cytokine release.¹⁰⁷ Another study found human endometrial epithelial cells upregulated TNF α cytokine expression following exposure to 6PPD and upregulated LIF cytokine expression following 6PPD-Q exposure.⁹⁰

Studies have also found increased inflammation in aquatic species. In coho salmon, 6PPD-Q upregulated the expression of proinflammatory molecules TNF α and il1 β .² In zebrafish, 6PPD caused dysregulation of the inflammatory response as indicated by a significant decrease in TNF α , IL-6 and IL-10 gene expression. An inflammation response was still triggered by 6PPD as the toxin increased the expression of NF- κ B pathway genes regulating fast, acute inflammation. Current research indicates the effects of 6PPD, and 6PPD-Q often manifest in upregulation of inflammatory pathways as well as proinflammatory cytokine release.⁹⁸

3. Lipid Accumulation

6PPD and 6PPD-Q induce lipid accumulation by dysregulating lipid metabolism in zebrafish.^{86,87,98} Comparison of the two environmental pollutants exposure in zebrafish revealed 6PPD caused a more aggressive lipid accumulation than 6PPD-Q.¹⁰⁸ Altered lipid metabolism was indicated by an upregulation of genes regulating lipid synthesis.⁸⁷ Similarly, 6PPD-Q exposure in *C. elegans* resulted in upregulation of genes regulating fatty acid synthesis and downregulation of genes regulating beta oxidation.⁷⁷ This led to increased triglyceride content and lipid droplet size. Further research indicated a transgenerational increase in lipid accumulation. This was bolstered by a transgenerational increase of genes regulating fatty acid synthesis and a decrease of genes regulating beta oxidation.⁸⁰

6PPD was found to disturb lipid metabolism in rats and 6PPD-Q exposure in mice resulted in lipid deposition via enhanced biosynthesis.^{65,109} This culminated in fatty liver disease in the mice following three weeks of 6PPD-Q exposure.⁶⁵ 6PPD-Q was also found to promote lipid synthesis and decrease lipolysis resulting in increased cholesterol and triglyceride levels in frogs.¹¹⁰ Various organisms have been found to accumulate lipids following exposure to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. This indicates serious risk of hepatotoxicity for organisms with a high likelihood of experiencing long term exposure to the tire pollutants as detrimental effects may include fatty liver disease.

Figure 1. Comprehensive overview of known interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q (created using BioRender.com).

Future Trends in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q Research

This holistic review summarized 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's toxicological effects on aquatic and terrestrial organisms highly susceptible to these tire pollutants. Terrestrial mammals and invertebrates were also included for comparison. With the expectation of providing insight to common intracellular pathways and mechanisms targeted, we focused on outlining metabolomics, transcriptomics, protein interactions and epigenetics. Despite the breadth in studies considered for this review, few connections between species dependent mechanisms and pathways were inferred. Alternatively, numerous conflicting discoveries, specifically morphological changes and mortality rates within zebrafish, were discerned. With 6PPD and 6PPD-Q recently emerging as hazardous environmental pollutants, considerable research gaps regarding the toxins require further attention (Figure 2). Based on the cumulative data presented in this review we have compiled a list of possible future research trends that may contribute to more accurate regulations:

1. **EPA regulation.** As of today, there are no EPA regulations stating the maximum level 6PPD or 6PPD-Q can reach in the environment. Because the toxicity of these tire antiozonants has only recently been discovered there is little to no research on the environmental effects. The EPA is working to provide funding for tire wear emissions, fate of 6PPD, where it accumulates, and toxicology studies. As well as providing funding for continuous research, the EPA is also spreading awareness of the possible pollutant to many native American tribes. These tribes rely heavily on salmon populations to sustain their people. Therefore, 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, which are known to be toxic to a variety of salmon species, threaten both animals and humans alike. Additional trends in research listed below may contribute to expediting the EPA regulation process.
2. **Expansion upon consequences throughout organisms' lifecycle.** Across the many studies of organismal response to 6PPD-Q two categories are apparent: tolerant and sensitive species. Tolerant species have a much higher threshold of 6PPD-Q they can endure before showing toxicity effects, while sensitive species exhibit stress responses, like elevated breathing rate, at low concentrations.⁸³ Additional categorization of species as tolerant or sensitive is necessary. Therefore, focusing on the differences between coho salmon, a sensitive species and zebrafish, a tolerant species, could reveal specific lifestage tolerance differences. Currently the knowledgebase surrounding coho salmon and zebrafish focus on embryonic forms and juvenile life stages.^{2,5,7,10,11,13,15,58-60} Moving forward implementation of studies comparing physiological effects induced in all life stages of zebrafish, other fish species, and coho salmon would provide a comprehensive understanding and interesting comparison between species.
3. **Toxicological effects on fungal cells.** Fungi are an integral aspect of water ecosystems. Fungal communities give vital information about the health of the ecosystem they reside in. No studies have ventured into the effects of PPDs on fungal cells. This could be an interesting approach to discern the ecosystem and eukaryotic effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. As fungal cells are single-celled eukaryotes, cell trafficking and protein interactions can easily be studied. Implementation of yeast studies opens the door to faster turnaround of data

acquisition as well as multi-faceted research approaches, such as metabolomics, transcriptomics, and bioaccumulation.

4. **Fertility across species and transgenerational effects.** 6PPD and 6PPD-Q have been identified as toxins to reproductive health in mice. The focus has been on male mice and the disruption of spermatogenesis.^{61–67} Although male reproduction is important it is critical to also investigate the effects of PPDs on female reproductive health. Therefore, it would be highly beneficial to study the impacts of female fertility and how PPDs affect future generations. These transgenerational effects may link to potential epigenetic changes across species.
5. **Fate of metabolites and their interactions *in vivo*.** Information regarding the Phase I and Phase II metabolites of 6PPD-Q has progressed rapidly. As PPDs become more prominent in the environment, detailing the fate and toxicity of these metabolites is a top priority. Creating potential pathways of biotransformation's and fates of metabolites is heavily important in pinning down potential biological markers to be used in exposure studies. Additionally, studies covering the metabolites of 6PPD are few. The biological markers for both chemicals may be different, even though 6PPD-Q is a derivative of 6PPD.
6. **Metagenomics approach.** Another interesting trend in future research is the implementation of metagenomics. Since 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are prominent water pollutants, analyzing the diversity of microorganisms in waterways with high levels of tire pollutants is necessary. Comparison of waterways, polluted and non-polluted, would provide differences in microbial community demographics. Additionally, microorganisms provide valuable information about water quality. Some microbes also can detoxify harmful materials. Using metagenomics to identify detoxifying bacteria present in polluted water may lead to potential bioremediation of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q using bacterial species.
7. **6PPD and 6PPD-Q effects on cancer cell lines.** There is limited knowledge of how 6PPD and 6PPD-Q interact with cancerous cells.²⁴ Using cancer cells as a model system is advantageous because of the ease of culturing and wide availability. Since cancerous cell lines are immortalized, preparing long term studies investigating toxicological effects is made possible. Additionally, cancer cells offer great insight to processes such as programmed cell death, viability and oxidative stress. These assessments are essential to uncovering the mechanisms behind PPD toxicity and serve as a good model to investigate remediation effects of different chemicals.¹⁰⁴
8. **Proteomics.** This area of study will help link the information presented in transcriptomic and metabolomic research. Protein interaction studies have been a large proponent of discerning the mechanism of action of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q however little is known about the changes in protein structure when in the presence of PPDs.
9. **Epigenetic knowledge expansion.** Epigenetics has become more common in toxicology studies however as of March 2025, there is only one study investigating epigenetic effects of 6PPD-Q.⁸⁸ Shifting focus from transcriptomic evaluation to study the epigenetic effects of both PPDs covered in this review could yield novel research. Assessing the transgenerational effects of PPDs on

DNA would be highly informative and give better insight into how these toxic chemicals work. Epigenetic changes may be one reason as to why 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are so toxic.

10. Single cell sequencing. Various studies using different model organisms and cell lines have been published showing toxic effects of PPDs. However, effects on different organs have yet to be investigated. Single-cell sequencing will remedy this by giving insight into how different organ cells react to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q exposure. This methodology can be used to illustrate the potential toxicological effects across organ systems. As 6PPD and 6PPD-Q research progresses, single-cell sequencing should be the next step.

Figure 2. Summary of future trends in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies (created using BioRender.com).

All the above-mentioned future research trends are equally important in advancing scientific understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Collectively, each area of emphasis will bridge the gaps in knowledge and provide a more thorough understanding of tire pollutant impacts. Eventually, this ground-breaking research will help formulate EPA regulations and combat the toxic effects of PPDs.

Author Contributions

E.B.: writing-original draft preparation, review, editing; M.M.: writing-original draft preparation, review, editing; K.K.: review, editing, and supervision. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Disclosure of interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable as no new data was created or analyzed in this review.

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